

Geological characterization of Tsiolkovskiy crater as a possible landing site for rover-based lunar exploration

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Tsiolkovskiy crater, located on the far side of the Moon, is considered the best example of farside mare volcanism. It is a Late Imbrian elliptical crater with a minor axis diameter of 180 km centered at 20.4° S, 129.1° E (Whitford-Stark & Hawke, 1982). The crater floor, which shows an elevation difference between its northern and southern portions (Mouginis-Mark & Boyce, 2017), presents a particularly dark mare deposit and an exclusively bright and well-preserved central peak, in which has been defined the presence of anorthosite composed of nearly 100% anorthite, also defined as Purest ANorthosite (PAN) (Ohtake et al., 2009; Lemelin et al., 2015), and olivine (Corley et al., 2018).

The above mentioned characteristics and the unusually smooth surface of the crater floor make Tsiolkovskiy crater a scientifically interesting and safe place for a possible landing site. Aiming to focus the strategy of exploration with rovers by means of planned traverses, we are producing geological maps of the site to select locations of high interest for investigations and analysis.

The main basemap used to characterize the surface morphology of the impact crater is the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Wide Angle Camera (LROC-WAC) (Robinson et al., 2010) mosaic with a resolution up to 100 m/pixel along with elevation data derived from the Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA) and Kaguya DEM merge (Barker et al., 2016). Tsiolkovskiy’s rim delimits the mapping area inside which have been defined the crater floor units (i.e. central peak, smooth and hummocky material) and the crater walls units (i.e. rim, steep scarps and smooth ponds).

The geomorphological mapping has then been coupled with the spectral characterization of Tsiolkovskiy crater performed on the basis of the a ~200 m/pixel false color composite generated using the Clementine UVVIS reflectance image (Lucey et al., 2000). The mapping has been performed on the basis of the different color of the units, associated to a different origin and composition of the material, which are mostly directly correlated to the morphological units.

Once the geological mapping will be concluded, an area of the crater will be selected and a study at higher resolution, by means of LROC Narrow Angle Camera images (Robinson et al., 2010), will be performed in order to define possible rover traverses.

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